

Prolonged solitary confinement of the Gdeim Izik Prisoners currently held in Tiflet2 Prison, Morocco

Solitary confinement is defined as a form of confinement where prisoners spend 22 to 24 hours a day alone in their cell in separation from others without meaningful human contact.

Rule 43(1b) of the Mandela Rules: the practice of Prolonged solitary confinement in itself amounts to torture or other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment, as established by the UN Special Rapporteur on Torture.¹

Currently four of 19 prisoners of the Gdeim Izik group are held in Tiflet2 prison over 1300km from El Aaiun, their hometown in Western Sahara where they were abducted and put in arbitrary detention in 2010.

Mr. Abbahah², Mr. Bourial³, Mr. Haddi⁴ and Mr. Khadda⁵ have been sentenced in a military court in 2013 and anew in a civil court in 2017 without having been presented proofs other than documents produced by the police and signed by the accused under torture. The Gdeim Izik group is composed currently by 19 prisoners detained in different prisons in the Moroccan Kingdom.⁶ Since the detention conditions in Tiflet2 are even worse then in the remaining prisons and the distance from Western Sahara superior than from the other prisons, I have decided to write this paper as an example of the extreme ill treatment and torture the prisoners of this Group have to endure, nine years after their arbitrary detention and after two trials with the confirmation of he final sentencing still pending the confirmation of the Moroccan Court de Cassation (Supreme Court) since 2017.⁷

This short information refers only to the situation of these prisoners detained in Tiflet2 prison, and only on the impacts of the prolonged solitary confinement they endure, although the remaining prisoners of the Group are equally victims of this kind of ill treatment and torture.

¹ *Special Rapporteur on Torture report 2011, A/66/268, e. g. paras. 21, 58 and 81.*

² Sidi Abdallah Abbahah sentenced to Life imprisonment

³ Mohamed Bourial sentenced to 30 years

⁴ Mohamed Lamin Haddi sentenced to 25 years

⁵ El Bachir Khadda sentenced to 20 years

⁶ <https://www.scribd.com/document/366418567/The-Gdeim-Izik-Case>

⁷ <https://www.scribd.com/document/366418567/The-Gdeim-Izik-Case>

Solitary confinement may be imposed on prisoners as short-term punishment for prison offences, or indefinitely for the prisoner's own protection, either at his request or at the discretion of the prison authorities. In other cases prisoners may be isolated from others for months and even years on administrative grounds: as a long-term strategy for managing challenging prisoners or where prisoners are deemed to be a threat to national security. Finally, pre-charge and pre-trial detainees may be isolated from others whilst their interrogation or the investigation into their case is ongoing.

Sharon Shalev in "A source book on solitary confinement"

In the case of the Saharawi Political Prisoners of the Gdeim Izik Group none of the above applies, the prolonged solitary confinement, with intervals of total isolation, is not to punish their behaviour, nor for their own protection nor for administrative reasons, the prisoners also do not represent a threat since their sentences range from 20 years to life imprisonment, nor are they "challenging".

The goal of the prolonged solitary confinement in the case of these Saharawi political prisoners is to break their spirits, to destroy their sanity and is one of many tortures they have undergone since their arbitrary arrest.

Not only are they 22h to 23h or more in solitary confinement they are also victims of sensory deprivation, without meaningful interaction with other human being.

Mr. El Bachir Khadda and Mr. Mohamed Lamin Haddi spent the 22 to 23 hours in their cells for months without tv, radio, books or other reading material. In solitary confinement since 16th September 2017.

The cells are small, without the minimum hygiene standards, ill ventilated, extremely cold in the winter, hot in the summer and with mould.

The prisoners have the right to very short visits of a close family member and short phone calls to the families. These visits do not occur frequently due to the huge distance between El Aaiun in Western Sahara where their family live and Tiflet, they are also frequently denied at the last minute without explanation. Maître Olfa Ouled has repeatedly asked to visit all of her clients but so far the Moroccan authorities did not only not give a positive answer, they also expelled Maître Ouled from Morocco in one of her attempts to locally organize the visit to the prisoners.

Mr. Abdallah Abbahah spends 24h in his cell, he also was for several weeks without books or radio and even a pen was denied to him when he asked to write a complaint

to the prison administration. In prolonged confinement since his transfer to Tiflet on the 7th May 2018. He has been continuously ill treated, harassed, suffered physical abuse and racist insults. In the last week of February 2019 he has received death threats from the guards.

Mr. Mohamed Bourial spends 22-23 hours in his cell. In solitary confinement since his transfer to Tiflet on the 7th May 2018 September 2018 until his temporary transfer to Bouzakarn prison (also in confinement) for a period of 93 days on June 11th 2018 , he returned to Tiflet2 and was put in the area for mentally ill prisoners for several periods of time and in prolonged solitary confinement most of the time.

In the few occasions that some of these prisoners have met other prisoners in the courtyard or on the way to the courtyard those prisoners are encouraged to insult and harass them and the guards also address them in aggressive tones, issuing menaces, insults and racist remarks. On the 26th of June 2018, Mr. Bourial was menaced with a knife by a prisoner with psychiatric disorders in the courtyard, after this incident he was attacked again without being protected by the prison guards.

In the module of Mr. Khadda other prisoners are forbidden to engage in conversations with him and if they do, they are punished.

Mr. Abdallah Abbahah's "yardtime" is always alone without any other prisoner and in a tiny exterior space with high walls and almost no sunlight. Mr. Abbahah did not have any significant human interaction since May 2017 except for a few visits from his family.

The four Saharawi political prisoners are separated in different modules of the prison and can never see or speak to each other, having different hours for visits and never see each other in the courtyard.

All four prisoners pursued their studies in the prison, Mr. Khadda and Mr. Haddi continue to study but denounced several times that they are prohibited to have the necessary means to prepare themselves for exams.

The prolonged solitary confinement and the sensory deprivation are only one aspect of the continues violations of the rights of these prisoners and the torture, ill treatment and abuse they have been subjected to. Related to the solitary confinement however, I have to address the issue of the extreme medical neglect and

even medical mal practice the Saharawi Political prisoners suffer and also these prisoners are victims of. Not only are they not treated for their diseases and pains, most of them due to the torture they have undergone⁸, but also does the medical staff not intervene to protect the psychological health of the prisoners in clear violation of both national as international law, and a breach of the Hippocratic oath. Furthermore, in the case of Mr. Abbahah several blood tests were performed without him being informed about the objective of the exams nor the results. Abbahah has acute tooth pain and is bleeding from his mouth for several months without being seen by a dentist nor having any medical treatment, the deficiency in the food provided, lacking fundamental nutrients and vitamins as well as the lack of day light and exercise increases the already frail health state.

Mr. Bourial has repeatedly denounced that he has acute chest pain without being visited by a doctor.

The Committee against Torture of the UN (CAT) issued interim measures after Maître Olfa Ouled, defence Lawyer of the Gdeim Izik group, presented individual complaints, however the measures were not respected nor taken into account by the Moroccan authorities, the process of the complaints is ongoing and confidential in accordance with the CAT procedures.

According to the Moroccan law 23-98⁹ regarding the administration and functioning of prisons, isolation periods cannot be longer than 45 days, books are allowed as well as regular visits from family and medical assistance has to be granted.

The right of prisoners to be treated in a manner respectful of their human dignity and the prohibition against all forms of torture, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment are amongst others in two international treaties that the Moroccan Kingdom ratified; the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR)¹⁰ and the UN Convention Against Torture (CAT). Morocco also ratified the Optional Protocol to the CAT (OPCAT) which aim is to prevent torture and other ill-treatment through a system of regular inspection visits to all places of deprivation of liberty. The OPCAT establishes both an international inspection body (the Sub-

⁸ <https://www.scribd.com/document/334623581/Report-on-Torture-Human-Right-Violation-and-Health-Condition-Denounced-by-the-24-sahrawi-prisoners-of-Gdeim-Izik>

⁹ <http://www.ilo.ch/dyn/natlex/docs/SERIAL/54210/51054/F-799221390/MAR-54210.pdf>

¹⁰ <https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/ccpr.aspx>

Committee for the Prevention of Torture) and a permanent national inspecting body (known as the National Preventative Mechanism).

In 2018 the subcommittee against torture visited the Moroccan Kingdom after the government had decided that the CNDH (Conseil National de Droit de Homme) would be the national mechanism, it did not however visit any Saharawi Political prisoners.

The Moroccan Kingdom has also to respect the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (the Nelson Mandela Rules)¹¹

However, the Moroccan Kingdom does not transport into reality the documents it signs and the laws it writes being the example of these group of prisoners an example of this discrepancy and the systematic torture and ill treatment the prisoners are subjected to, by the orders and with the knowledge of the highest authorities, which are fully aware of the situation since they have received dozens of complaints presented by the families and their lawyer Maître Olfa Ouled.

Also, the CNDH has been notified of all infringements and violations but never answers the family's complaints.

The severe and long-lasting damage isolation can cause to human beings has been documented and Medical research confirms that the denial of meaningful human contact can cause 'isolation syndrome', the symptoms of which include anxiety, depression, anger, cognitive disturbances, perceptual distortions, paranoia, psychosis, self-harm and suicide, and can destroy a person's personality.¹²

Meaningful human contact is measured by the amount and quality of social interaction and psychological stimulation which human beings require for their mental health and well-being, therefore:

- human contact has to be face to face and direct (without physical barriers). In

¹¹ https://www.unodc.org/documents/justice-and-prison-reform/GA-RESOLUTION/E_ebook.pdf

¹²Grassian S, 'Psychiatric effects of solitary confinement', *Journal of Law and Policy*, Vol. 22, 2006, pp. 325-383 (*Psychiatric effects of solitary confinement*); Craig Haney, 'Mental health issues in long-term solitary and "supermax" confinement', *Crime & Delinquency*, Vol. 49, No. 1, 2003, pp. 124-156; Sharon Shalev, *A sourcebook on solitary confinement*, Mannheim Centre for Criminology, London School of Economics, 2008 (*A sourcebook on solitary confinement*); UN General Assembly, 66th Session, *Interim report of the Special Rapporteur of the Human Rights Council on torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment*, 5 August 2011, A/66/268 (*Special Rapporteur on Torture report 2011*).

the case of these prisoners even during some of the family the visits they were separated by a grid in the visit room;

- the contact cannot be limited to interactions during prison routines, such as prison guards handing them food or medication to the cell door
- communication by shouting at each other through cell walls or door grids are not considered meaningful contact

These prisoners are clearly deprived from the necessary stimuli that conduct to a meaning full human contact, since there is no empathetic exchange nor sustained, social interaction.

According to the medical experts' isolation and solitary confinement constitute also a high-risk situation for human rights abuse.¹³ and placement in solitary confinement can increase the risk of suicide.¹⁴ In the case of the Tiflet2 prisoners the solitary confinement is linked with limitations in access to family visits and therefore its negative impact is heightened.

Psychological and Physical effects have been documented over several decades by researchers¹⁵ :

Physical effects

- Heart palpitations (awareness of strong and/or rapid heartbeat while at rest)
- Diaphoresis (sudden excessive sweating)
- Insomnia
- Back and other joint pains
- Deterioration of eyesight
- Poor appetite, weight loss and sometimes diarrhoea
- Lethargy, weakness
- Tremulousness (shaking)
- Feeling cold
- Aggravation of pre-existing medical problems.

¹³ Penal Reform International/Association for the Prevention of Torture, *Balancing security and dignity in prisons: a framework for preventive monitoring: 2nd edition*, 2016, p. 14 (*Balancing security and dignity 2nd edition*).

¹⁴ WHO/International Association for Suicide Prevention, *Preventing Suicide in Jails and Prisons*, Geneva, 2007, p.16.

¹⁵ Grassian & Friedman (1986); Grassian (2006); Haney & Lynch (1997); Haney (2003); Scharff-Smith (2006).

Psychological effects

Anxiety, ranging from feelings of tension to full blown panic attacks

- Persistent low level of stress
- Irritability and/or anxiousness
- Fear of impending death
- Panic attacks

Depression, varying from low mood to clinical depression

- Emotional flatness/blunting – loss of ability to have any ‘feelings’
- Emotional lability (mood swings)
- Hopelessness
- Social withdrawal; loss of initiation of activity or ideas; apathy; lethargy
- Major depression

Anger, ranging from irritability to full blown rage

- Irritability and hostility,
- Poor impulse control
- Outbursts of physical and verbal violence against others, self and objects
- Unprovoked anger, sometimes manifesting as rage

Cognitive disturbances, ranging from lack of concentration to confusional states

- Short attention span
- Poor concentration
- Poor memory
- Confused thought processes; disorientation.

Perceptual distortions, ranging from hypersensitivity to hallucinations

- Hypersensitivity to noises and smells
- Distortions of sensation (e.g. walls closing in)
- Disorientation in time and space
- Depersonalization/derealisation
- Hallucinations affecting all five senses, visual, auditory, tactile, olfactory and gustatory (e.g. hallucinations of objects or people appearing in the cell, or hearing voices when no-one is actually speaking).

Paranoia and Psychosis, ranging from obsessional thoughts to full blown psychosis

- Recurrent and persistent thoughts (ruminations) often of a violent and vengeful character (e.g. directed against prison staff)
- Paranoid ideas – often persecutory
- Psychotic episodes or states: psychotic depression, schizophrenia.

The Nelson Mandela Rules are clear about the absolute prohibitions of the practice of solitary confinement, but also further limitations as for instance that it should only be applied *in exceptional cases as a last resort, for as short a time as possible and subject to independent review, and only pursuant to the authorization by a competent authority.*¹⁶ The prohibitions and limitations mentioned in the Nelson Mandela Rules apply regardless of the purpose of the practice, i.e. whether applied as a disciplinary sanction, or citing safety and security reasons. Included in the absolute prohibitions of the use of solitary confinement is the prolonged solitary confinement, and it can be considered prolonged when the prisoner does not know when the confinement will end.

These prisoners entered several hunger strikes being the longest that of Mr. Abbahah for 44 days and Mr. Khadda 43 days which started in October 2018 and ended on the 13th November 2018.

Mohamed Bourial who went on hunger strike on 20th March 2019 suspended his strike on April 18th 2019 after 30 days.

None of the demands of the prisoners were granted despite the promises of the Moroccan authorities nor did these prisoners have medical attention during the hunger strikes.

Conclusion

Since:

The Moroccan Kingdom enforces prolonged solitary confinement on Mr. Abbahah, Mr. Bourial, Mr. Haddi and Mr. Khadda, albeit the clear violation of National and International law, and covenants and agreements signed by the Moroccan

¹⁶ Rule 45 of the Nelson Mandela Rules

Government and the complaints presented at national and international levels by the families and their lawyer Maître Olfa Ouled the situation did not change;

And:

The UN - OHCHR mechanisms are all informed about the situation of these prisoners on a regular basis, and several complaints have been sent;

Also, the European Union through its parliamentarians is informed about the situation and the High Representative for foreign affairs, answered systematically that the EU follows the case with concern and is in contact with the Moroccan government and the CNDH;

It is urgent that:

- The Moroccan Kingdom complies with national and international law and stops immediately the prolonged solitary confinement allowing the four prisoners to be joined in the same prison module, access to radio and books, regular visits from their family members and adequate medical assistance;
- The mechanisms of the OHCHR and the ICRC visit the Saharawi Political Prisoners

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